

Point of care workflow management system to improve head and neck cancer survivors follow up and quality of life monitoring.

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Abstract. People treated for head and neck cancer (HNC) frequently face many difficulties in self-managing their daily life and need to overcome diverse social and health-related barriers. Thus, a coordinated and proactive personalized health care to monitor after treatment follow-up, quality of life (QoL) and to actively support lifestyle recommendations is urgently needed. In this work we present a Workflow Management System (WfMS) using not only clinical records but also QoL related data, embedding these data sources into clinical trial protocols. Within the context of the BD4QoL European project, an innovative Point of Care (PoC) application to support HNC survivor's follow-up has been created following user-centered design principles: an online validation form shared with 21 stakeholders, 2 focus groups conducted with 21 participants and 10 workshops with 14 healthcare professionals. Evaluation surveys conducted with 10 beta testers showed positive impact in terms of acceptance and usefulness. During the BD4QoL trial, the patient's clinical data is obtained from electronic Case Report Forms (eCRFs), QoL is measured from validated web questionnaires and lifestyle and motivational data is gathered using a tailored mobile app. Based on these data, the PoC WfMS has been developed to facilitate physicians the assessment of patients' evolution and to adapt follow-up consultations. This novel vision of a WfMS will support anticipating risks and informing patients and caregivers of personalized interventions to timely intercept and prevent any possible long-term effects of treatment, either physical or emotional.

Keywords: Workflow Management System, Head and Neck Cancer, Quality of Life.

1 Introduction

Head and neck cancer (HNC) encompasses a diverse spectrum of tumours located on the upper aerodigestive tract, its annual incidence reaches more than 700,000 new cases and over 350,000 deaths per year, and after decades of decline, the incidence rates

have increased by 0.8% in the last years, subsequently mortality also increased slightly, with a mean survival rate of 67% for tumours located in the oral cavity and pharynx [1]. Depending on the characteristics and location of the tumour, treatment usually consists of surgery interventions or chemo-radiotherapy, unfortunately leading to long term effects and late effects. HNC survivors often need after-treatment rehabilitation for eating and speaking and are susceptible to develop mental health problems and to experience negative emotions due to a life-changing situation. Self-management helps cancer survivors to deal with these challenges supported by the limited health sources available [2]. Thus, the health and well-being of HNC survivors requires close attention to multiple factors through carefully designed care delivery plans.

Post-treatment cancer care typically includes the monitoring of long term effects and late effects through routine medical visits, scheduled rehabilitation and general daily life recommendations [3]. These standardized healthcare guidelines became insufficient for survivorship, lacking coordinated, proactive, and personalized management at both hospitals and in primary care [4]. Incidentally, person-centred care considering not only health records but also personal needs and preferences, attending to physical and psychological challenges, promotes disease awareness, acceptance, and relief, and has proven to achieve better survival rates and encouragement among patients, while providing detailed resources to professionals for individual supporting care [5]. Recent improvements in cancer care delivery and survivorship follow-up also allowed the inclusion of Quality of Life (QoL) measurements as essential factors to determine the effectiveness of clinical management after treatment and to provide personalized assistance [6,7]. Follow-up care plans that include QoL measures, in combination with daily monitoring systems, are expected to be more accurate in terms of early detection of recurrence -when small areas of cancer cells that remained undetected start to increase in number- as evolution of symptoms and subtle evidence are being analysed frequently [8]. However, the optimal integration of standard of care, Quality of Life measurements, daily monitoring and subsequent results in a common platform requires a proper Workflow Management System (WfMS).

Workflow management systems aim to deliver, interpret, and present the information inferred from multiple sources to the different stakeholders involved in patients' follow up (e.g., oncologists, surgeons, GPs, caregivers, speech therapists and physiotherapists) at different Points of Care. This is expected to augment the knowledge available to health- and social-care professionals to support them making better decisions, and personalize follow-up plans according to specific health related Quality of Life (HRQoL) and evolution of single patients.

The BD4QoL project implemented a Point of Care (PoC) support service, centred on a Workflow Management System, which aims to provide the previously mentioned new types of information, detected through an innovative data collection platform, to the right health and social care professionals at the different PoCs involved in patient follow up. This includes advanced methods for data interpretation and visualization as well as the timely generation of alerts in case issues arise that require the intervention of clinicians and other care professionals. The provision of an empowerment platform to offer methodically organized data from patients, useful information, recommendations, and a communication channel with clinicians, will impact quality and timeliness

of responses to HRQoL and health status evolution. Thus, the Point of Care tool is a tailored application deployed to clinicians' work teams that allows them to manage and carry out daily activities and procedures more efficiently during the follow-up of head and neck cancer patients [9], but the PoC application is also a decision support system and workflow management system that collects data from patients both through the BD4QoL mobile app and patient inputted values in routine questionnaires.

The design of the BD4QoL cost-effective approach and organizational framework for HNC cancer survivors' management requires a clinical validation and translation into medical practice. To this aim, during a prospective trial with 24 months duration, real time input from physicians in charge of supporting HNC survivor's follow-up will be gathered. Additionally, at the beginning and at the end of the experimental study, patients and healthcare professionals involved in the study will be provided with a set of surveys to evaluate the usability of the system and their satisfaction. Favourable results would imply advances for improving person-centred HNC follow-up healthcare in terms of efficiency, early detection of symptoms and promotion of healthy lifestyles, to ultimately foster better outcomes and patients' reassurance.

2 Materials and Methods

The development of the Workflow Management system for HNC patients is focused on the needs of both cancer survivors and clinicians responsible for their follow-up. First, activities about collecting and understanding information related to the stakeholders and the context where the technology will be implemented were done conducting a literature review, a scoping review and market research of PoC systems within the e-health market [10]. After the comprehensive analysis of this information, the following activities were conducted to design a preliminary version of the application [11]:

- An online validation form was shared with 21 stakeholders in order to collect the profile details about future users of the tool and to consolidate the context-related and state-of-the-art information previously analysed.
- 2 focus groups were conducted with 21 participants to gain the perspective of the professionals involved in the Point of Care clinical workflow, to design a novel clinical workflow applying the proposed tools and to discuss the functionalities, requirements, and purpose of these tools. The profiles of the 21 participants included nurses, oncologists, radiotherapists, surgeons, psychologists, and hospital managers.
- After these activities, a first version of the tool was implemented, followed by 10 workshops with 14 healthcare professionals conducted to measure functional results, to obtain valuable feedback from the users' analysis of the visual and functional aspects of the systems, and to perform a continuous validation of the technology during its development.

These activities are fundamental to understand the real needs of HNC patients and clinicians. In current practice, cancer survivorship monitoring mostly focuses on periodic medical screening for clinical conditions such as new diseases, physical dis-functioning and psychological distress. Wider QoL aspects such as social inclusion, self-

image and stigmatization, economic problems hampering access to specialized rehabilitation are considered in established health-related quality of life (HRQoL) instruments, that will be applied in the BD4QoL clinical study.

Eligible patients for the BD4QoL study are subjects being followed up after curative treatments for head and neck cancers, and patients enrolled in the study will participate for up to 24 months. For those patients, HRQoL can be evaluated through the QLQ-C30 questionnaire from the European Organization for Research and Treatment of Cancer (EORTC), especially important for being cancer-specific and widely validated. These questionnaires will be repeated every 6 months, in order to track the evolution of global health status, HNC-related symptoms and overall functionality, including physical, cognitive, social and emotional functioning. Another specific QoL questionnaire is the QLQ-HN43, to gather information about the extent of the possible after-treatment symptoms, such as problems chewing and swallowing. These two questionnaires are complemented with another three questionnaires: The Cancer Behavior Inventory (CBI-B) for a brief measure of self-efficacy, the 5-level EQ-5D version (EQ-5D-5L) to record the patient's self-rated health, and the Patient Reported Experience Measure (PREM) to measure the perception of the patient's experience while receiving care. The complete assessment of QoL, reported periodically during the prospective study, provides comprehensive information about the evolution of patients, allowing personalized medical care adjustments and helps predicting health deterioration, as these QoL questionnaires are integrated as part of the BD4QoL Workflow Management System.

The BD4QoL Workflow Management System comprises different functionalities: 1) patient enrolment-withdrawn administration to support trial management, 2) collection of CRF data, 3) visits management, and 4) alert management which detects and notifies when a patient has a behaviour decay or symptoms requiring intervention. To carry out these functionalities, REDCap (Research Electronic Data Capture) [12] has been used, a tool that allows to create and manage online forms to collect data for research studies and that is broadly used in clinical trials. Through this tool, the eligibility form is filled out and the patients are randomized to enrol in the study. In addition, all the information related to the CRF data is also collected, and the visits are managed, filling in the forms with the information collected from the patient during the visit. For the withdrawal of patients from the study, it is also done through REDCap, where clinicians fill out a form to withdraw the patient from the study, indicating the reason for the withdrawal and whether the patient wants their data to be kept or not. Lastly, regarding the alert management system, the alerts related to the patient's symptoms are obtained through conversations between the patient and a smart chatbot within the mobile app. The rest of the patient's clinical alerts are obtained by analysing the patient's usual behaviour through the data collected daily related to the patient's activity, sleep and social life.

All data collected through the REDCap forms and during patient monitoring is stored at the data management infrastructure and visualized within the PoC tool. The PoC tool is used for data visualization, alerts management and visit management, where clinicians can visualize the data and access REDCap to fill out the forms. Additionally, the PoC interacts with the Chatbot (arrow connecting the Alerts management feature from the PoC to activate and manage the different alerts defined by physicians).

Figure 1 represents the complete PoC workflow. Five main modules are provided within the tool (orange), twelve screens (blue) and five modals (white). Once a physician is logged in to the tool, the *Patient information* module is active, which contains the list of all the patients enrolled in the clinical study center. From this section, you can access the visualization of the eCRF data or the individual patient data of any of the patients. This individual information contains a summary of the patient with the data collected through the mobile monitoring system, the questionnaire, visit and alert report and communication history of the patient. In addition, from the main patient information module, you can access the rest of the modules, which are the *Trial dashboard* module, which contains information on the visits and demographic and clinical information of all patients and the *Exploratory dashboard* module that allows to view the data from the questionnaires, activity, phone usage and affective traits of all patients. They are also connected to the *Visit management* module, visits' visualization and management, and lastly with the *Alerts management* module, for the alerts' visualization and management.

Fig. 1. Point of Care tool Workflow Management System. Relation between modules (orange), screens (blue) and modals (white).

The BD4QoL data management infrastructure where the Management Workflow is implemented offers all privacy-related services (authentication, authorization, GDPR compliance) at user and processes level. Privacy-enforcement mechanisms include strong passwords for every component and the mandatory use of encrypted SSL traffic between all services. Additionally, perimetral security using firewalls isolates the BD4QoL's virtual datacenter from the rest of the infrastructure where it is hosted. As different BD4QoL components share computing and storage space, these firewalls allow the establishment of access rules to limit the authorized sources that can access the services within the BD4QoL infrastructure. Finally, an SSL/TLS protocol is used to encrypt and transmit data securely, combined with Keycloak for identity and access management, and the HTTPS configuration of the web service is implemented with a certificate authority that is generated and renewed with the CertBot framework.

To test the workflow management system, a beta pilot test was carried out. During this pilot, different clinicians and technical experts participated to test the different tools and the flow of the system. To do this, users were asked to walkthrough on specific tasks. In addition, a user experience assessment was carried out, including a technological acceptance assessment, usability assessment, satisfaction assessment and quality of Mobile app assessment. Finally, to evaluate the tools, a Heuristic Evaluation (HE) was carried out, in which only the technical profiles participated. This HE had two phases, a first phase in which the launched application was evaluated, and a second phase in which the beta version of the tools was evaluated after implementing the changes identified during the first phase of the HE. The idea with the second iteration of the HE of the tools is to analyse the feedback coming from the “participation-observation study” and the results of the “user experience assessment” in order to validate the tools and identify final usability problems in the user interface design. The feedback obtained from this HE has been implemented to produce the final version of the BD4QoL tools to be used in the Pilot Validation.

3 Results

Patient centered WfMS

There is no commonly accepted standard of follow-up for HNC survivors. Therefore, the BD4QoL WfMS aspires to become a reliable model to increase the motivation of patients after treatment and achieve a more user-centred follow-up.

At the time the patient enrolls in the study, a visit is automatically scheduled for every six months, from the time of enrolment in the study until 24 months later. During the time of the study, data collected about the patient's status provides information such as whether a detected recurrence of cancer was noticed during the planned visit or any new non-cancer-related medical event. In case the patient has not the possibility to reach the hospital, data will be collected remotely and the outcomes from those visits will be requested lately. Besides, for each of the follow-up visits, patients fill out the five quality of life questionnaires: QLQ-C30, QLQ-HN43, CBI-B, EQ-5D-5L and PREM. The scores of each of the questionnaires are also visualized at the individual patient level in the PoC, where the clinicians will be able to analyse the responses of the patients to carry out a more detailed evaluation, and complete the information collected during the follow-up visit.

In addition to the data collected during the visits, daily monitoring of the patient is carried out by collecting information through the BD4QoL mobile app. This daily data collected includes the user's physical activity (steps stats, non-sleep events rate and activity journal) and phone usage (calls, messages, Wi-Fi connections, screen on time and time spent in social media). All these data are displayed in the PoC at an aggregated level and at single user level, where clinicians can analyse the data collected from each of the patients during the last weeks, months or years in order to detect any relevant change that can affect their health status or quality of life.

Furthermore, through the collected data, the usual behaviour of each of the patients is estimated to detect if there has been a deterioration in the patient's behaviour in the

last two weeks. In the case of detecting any behaviour deterioration, the system sends a notification to the clinician.

The BD4QoL system also has a smart chatbot embedded in the mobile app, that is able to take patients inquiries and even request the doctor's attention if the patient requires an intervention. The chatbot aims to provide patients with professional-verified information and additional support interactions to increase the empowerment and sources available, while keeping track of these interactions at the PoC tool providing innovative types of information to clinicians.

Patient management for risk anticipation

Through the daily motivation of patients, the proposed WfMS is intended to reduce the risk of QoL deterioration in HNC survivors. With the alert management system, all the data collected by the BD4QoL platform such as physical activity (measured through step count), non-sleep activity (through sensor-based data) and social activities (measured as phone usage and amount of different locations recorded by smartphone GPS) is analysed in a daily basis, and any variations activate notifications sent to the study participant through the mobile application, and to the PoC for professional revision.

The alerts generated are classified into two different types, alerts based on the behavior alteration and alerts based on symptom identification. Regarding alerts based on behavioral changes, the number of steps, non-sleep activity and phone usage time are studied each week. Depending on the variation in each of these fields, one type of alert or another is obtained. If the number in steps, non-sleep activity or phone usage is less than 50% of the usual in the last two weeks, the chatbot is activated and it asks the patient whether any health issue has occurred. If not, then the Chatbot automatically provides the patient with tips. If yes, then the chatbot questions the patient about which health issue occurred and automatically provides the patient with related tips for managing the health issue. For all these cases, in addition to the recommendations that the chatbot sends to the patient, an alert is generated that is sent to the PoC so that the clinicians can see it. All the alerts that are sent in this case are informative for the clinician, and do not require any type of information, except if the health issue reported by the patient is of high priority, in which case the doctor has to intervene and contact the patient. If steps, non-sleep activity or phone usage is less than 50% of usual for more than two weeks the Chatbot automatically asks the patient again whether any health issue has occurred. If not, then the Chatbot automatically provides the patient with motivational tips. If yes, then the chatbot questions the patient about which health issue occurred and automatically provides the patient with related tips for managing the health issue. Depending on whether the health issue is low, moderate or high priority, the chatbot performs one action or another. If it is of low priority, it asks the patient if they wish to have a medical consultation, while if it is moderate or high, it generates an alert and an intervention will be requested by the clinicians. Finally, if steps, non-sleep activity and phone usage are less than 50% from usual for further than two weeks (total six weeks) the Chatbot automatically asks the patient again whether any health issue has occurred. On this occasion If it has not happened, then the Chatbot automatically provides the patient with motivational tips. If yes, then the chatbot questions the patient

about which health issue occurred and sends an alert of low, moderate or high priority depending on the priority level of the health issue and an intervention will be requested.

Regarding alerts based on symptoms, after the first symptom is reported, the Chatbot is activated. If the symptom has low priority, the alert will not arrive at PoC; if the same symptom occurs, the Chatbot is activated again, and it will ask the patient whether they would like their healthcare provider to be notified; after the third reiteration of the symptom, a notification to the PoC will be sent. Depending on the priority of the symptoms, the alert appears with a different color in the PoC to prioritize those alerts that pose a greater risk to the patient's health. Symptoms are classified into three different priorities depending on their impact on the patient's health. The symptoms classified as moderate priority are negative emotions/depression, difficulty swallowing, fever, facial pain, change in social circumstances, neck swelling, weight loss, difficulty eating and loss of smell. While the symptoms classified as high priority are difficulty breathing, total blindness, bleeding eyes and ear pain.

With all this monitoring and alert management system, the aim is not only to detect a possible problem ahead of time, but also to be able to manage the possible health issues of the patients as soon as possible to reduce the risk to the patient's health as much as possible.

Ethical regulations

When treating sensitive data, it is fundamental to keep the anonymity of patients for all visualization tools and transfer between subsystems to ensure privacy rights protection. All data obtained through the PoC tool and REDCap platform associated to the BD4QoL project is engaged to a Data Transfer Agreement (DTA) based upon European Regulations No 1290/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013, laying down the rules for the participation and dissemination in the framework of Horizon 2020 Programme for Research and Innovation. Terms and conditions include that the data will not be used for commercial purposes and that only authorized users will be able to lawfully process these data. Along the development of this WfMS ethical regulations and DTA duties have been properly considered and fulfilled.

Beta version validation

Selected beta testers were provided with clinician credentials to access the PoC tool and evaluate the performance status of the beta version following the user's manual and platform walkthrough indications. The tests included an exhaustive examination of the management workflow of alerts and notifications, visits, eCRFs and dashboards visualization. All issues found during the beta testing were reported internally and fixed by the BD4QoL technical team. Once beta testers were familiar with the platform, to perform a deep feasibility assessment for validation with end users, we provided a set of standardized questionnaires and scales to measure technological acceptance, usability, satisfaction, and quality of the PoC tool beta version. The survey included five questionnaires: Basic profile questions, System Usability Scale (SUS) [13], Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) [14], AttrakDiff [15] and eHeals Literacy Scale [16]. This survey was distributed through an anonymous link to all the beta participants with a

clinician ID, using a software platform for experience management (Qualtrics, Provo, UT) to a total of 10 participants.

Evaluation survey results showed a positive impact in terms of acceptance and usefulness. The mean age of the participants was $34,90 \pm 8,88$. Their background was addressed based on their institution and expertise, being 70% part of a Healthcare Institution, 20% working on a Technology Company and 10% in an Academic Research Institution. Their expertise includes oncology, surgery, nursery, biology, technology, and software development.

For the SUS questionnaire (table 1) most of the users consider that they would like to use the system frequently, that it was easy to use and quickly to learn, that functions are well integrated, and they felt confident during the testing. Few found the system unnecessarily complex or that there was too much inconsistency, the majority also stated that they will not need support of a technical person and required not much previous knowledge. Regarding the Technology Acceptance (TAM) questions, 55% of the responses agree or strongly agree with the system being useful and having a general positive impact. Only 22% disagreed or strongly disagreed with the TAM questions and another 22% remained neutral. From the AttrakDiff questionnaire results, the system is described in general positive terms such as connective, pleasant, attractive, and professional. Finally, when participants were asked their opinion about their experience using the Internet for health information, 75% of the participants considered eHealth useful and the rest remained neutral. When they were asked about how important it is for them to be able to access health resources on the internet, 100% of the participants chose important or very important. Last questions revealed that most of the participants have some experience and feel confident with eHealth resources. These results show that, overall, the design and system usability of the PoC tool is in the right direction.

This 5-questionnaires survey has served as a first approximation to evaluate the usability of the system from the physician's perspective, and to establish a system validation from the sharing of questionnaires through an automatic anonymous link, to collection of the results and complete analysis. For the prospective study, basic profile questions will be reduced as all participants will belong to hospital or healthcare institutions, and results will be categorized also by the centre to consider regional bias.

Table 1. Results from the SUS questionnaire of the BD4QoL PoC tool. The mean varies from 0-strongly disagree to agree 5-strongly.

SUS question	Mean
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently.	3.45
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex.	2.73
3. I thought the system was easy to use.	3.64
4. I think I would need the support of a technical person.	2.36

5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated.	3.64
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in the system.	2.09
7. I think that most people would learn to use this system very quickly.	3.64
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use.	2.73
9. I felt very confident using the system.	3.64
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with the system.	2.09

4 Discussion

Early detection methods, information, and support to patients after cancer through coordinated care workflows that facilitate patients-PoC interactions during follow-up are highly demanded. By including other services such as activity recognition systems, affective traits detection, advanced visualization, or e-coaching, it is possible to orchestrate a whole novel system following the latest technological eHealth trends [17]. In addition, the services included in the BD4QoL WfMS will be extensible in the future, allowing a self-sustained Decision Support System (DSS). The potential of Management Workflows to efficiently access and maintain large amounts of data from patients is not only a necessity, but an opportunity to coordinate the complex architecture of processes within the healthcare system for notifications, interventions, and personal guidelines. These healthcare systems are no longer constrained to static procedures, their flexibility to adapt to the individual needs of every patient condition and evolution after treatment allows enhancing the quality of the attention and, at the same time, significantly lowering the cost of services by optimizing resources.

Despite the positive feedback received from the validation with beta testers, the number of participants is not sufficient to perform an evaluation of the results with strict statistical significance. Further assessments during an experimental study with HNC survivors are needed. The BD4QoL prospective study will be an opportunity to improve patients' follow-up with a reliable and deeply tested platform and gather large amounts of QoL data which is usually unavailable. This information will be most beneficial for the scientific community in terms of emphasizing patients' wellbeing in follow-up protocols, to train big data models for risk prediction and better understand aftereffects of treatment in daily life for HNC cancer survivors. For this information to be trustable, the WfMS has to be robust and consistent. Quality rules, a thorough logging system and a ticketing system to report issues within the platform have been implemented, ensuring that any problem encountered will be solved by the technical support team, to verify the reliability of all functionalities within the BD4QoL WfMS.

Once the BD4QoL prospective study finalizes and the quality of the data gathered and the services provided is validated, the system can be extended to patients with other specialties or pathologies within the approved hospitals. Similarly, the registration of

data can be tailored to include a broader spectrum of symptoms, visit timelines and quality of life measures. The Point of Care tool management system is also compatible with standard clinical systems and can be integrated into a hospital's infrastructure. The implementation requirements necessary to embed the whole BD4QoL platform into an institutional electronic health record (EHR), are under assessment to associate the BD4QoL data gathered with the same patients' identifiers stored in the data warehouse of a hospital and a Regional Health System, as well as the standardization of the data collected from different sources.

5 Conclusions

The use of a novel Workflow Management System that includes daily monitoring and periodic revisions of quality of life facilitates early recognition of symptoms, morbidities, and potentially actionable changes relevant for risk prediction. Adapting scheduled visits to the current health status of patients and building a direct communication bridge between patients and the local clinical team also enhances personalized and precise care delivery. This Workflow Management System, once validated in a clinical study, can be easily adapted to other cancers and healthcare domains. Such ambition entails a paradigm shift including survival, functional status, emotional status, other wellbeing domains and overall satisfaction at the centre of care delivery and post-treatment follow-up for cancer patients and other potential health domains, linking patients, health- and social-care professionals, and public health policy in a consistent network.

The availability of smartphones and other mobile devices among increasing segments of the population, and their continuous presence and usage, make them the ideal unobtrusive activity data collection platform. Combined with medical history, medical records from scheduled visits and quality of life questionnaires, the diversity of data gathered, carefully structured and embedded in the HNC survivors' management system, guarantees the detailed personalized supportive care and empowerment of cancer survivors. The era of smartphones, Big Data and eHealth claims for implementing and experiencing new tools and approaches to survivors' management that take advantage of the latest novelties, to timely intercept clinically relevant turning points that affects QoL, which are nowadays unknown or poorly appreciated. The WfMS of the BD4QoL project aims to provide significant impact on the prevention and early detection of HNC related issues, personalized adaptation of care plans, and fill in the gaps in the current practice of cancer survivorship monitoring.

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